

SPECIAL ISSUE: Urban and regional infrastructures

The Myth of Urban Densification: Tracing the Pathway of a Discourse on the Case of the Alpine Rhine Valley in Austria

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Abstract

Over the past several decades, urban densification has emerged as one of the predominant principles in spatial planning. Even though it is often portrayed in objective and quantitative ways, recent research concludes that urban densification is highly political and context specific. Therefore, this article explores how urban densification has emerged as a form of hegemony, utilising the case study of the Alpine Rhine Valley in western Austrian province of Vorarlberg. Long characterized by single-family-home-induced urban sprawl, urban densification has gained a prominent role in the region's policies and politics. By means of discourse analysis and Ernesto Laclau's conception of hegemony, this article retraces how urban densification emerged through two dislocatory crises, yet is still confronted with "rival articulations" from primarily conservative political actors. Urban densification is hence best described by Laclau's term "myth", which characterizes urban densification as an envisioned ideal state by a variety of social actors, but which fails to gain unequivocal support from civil society.

Keywords

urban densification, hegemony, discourse analysis, Laclau, Alpine Rhine Valley

Introduction

Over the past several decades, urban densification has emerged as one of the predominant principles in spatial planning. It has become embedded within contemporary planning ideals from the Smart City to Transit-oriented Development and New Urbanism; hence, many cities now cited as best-practice examples of sustainable urban development have implemented urban densification measures and policies. These cities arguably demonstrate that sustainable development *is* possible and urban densification *can* lead to positive results from a sustainability perspective, when considering aspects such as a reduction of land consumption,

decreasing levels of individual traffic or an increase in the efficiency in the provision of public and private infrastructure.

However, interests and aspirations associated with urban densification vary between different epochs of spatial planning, and the socio-economic conditions under which they arose (Keil, 2020, p. 1285). Therefore, urban densification must be studied across highly diverse contexts. In contrast to other studies of urban densification, which typically focus on short-term contexts, this article uses a Laclau-inspired discourse analysis to adopt a long-term perspective, retracing the emergence of urban densification as a form of hegemony in constant struggle with the prevailing discourse of the single-family-home. While authors such as Robinson and Attuyer (2020) and Rosol (2013) frame urban densification as coupled to financialization and neoliberal practices in spatial planning, this article argues that the roots of today's urban densification discourse lie significantly further in the past. The article thus provides new insight into framing density "as a dynamic and contingent political process that intersects with state practices to reveal trends in how cities and urbanization are transforming" (Chen et al., 2020, p. 2).

The Alpine Rhine Valley in western Austria is a prime subject for such research. Embedded into the extended urban fabric of the Lake Constance region, including international metropolitan areas such as Zurich and Munich, this area is a typical, ordinary small-city-region that exists below the threshold of urban studies. However, these regions are of critical importance for studies of urban densification, precisely because they are often characterised by the "large area of urbanized land that remains underexploited due to low residential density" (Touati-Morel, 2015, p. 604).

The Alpine Rhine Valley reveals its empirical value through the clarity and visibility of how the discourse on urban densification has experienced a change in fortune. Long shaped by the single-family home developments preferred by the reigning conservative people's party (ÖVP), the past few years saw urban densification gain a prominent role in the public discussion of spatial development; now, a plethora of heterogeneous actors rally around this planning principle. By presenting a long-term perspective and contrasting it with the role of single-family-homes in creating urban sprawl, this article explains how and why urban densification emerged as an ostensibly unanimously agreed-upon planning principle in the Alpine Rhine Valley.

First, the article discusses the literature on urban densification. Subsequently, the methodological approach is introduced, including the theory of hegemony and discourse analysis. After a short overview of the case study area, the article presents the empirical results using three steps derived from Ernesto Laclau's hegemony theory. The conclusion builds on these findings to provide an outlook for future research.

Conceptual Framework: The Rise of Urban Densification

Not even a century ago, the dense city was considered contrary to the ideals of an intact environment and a desirable quality of life. Shaped by the images of the industrial city, which included environmental degradation through industrialization and neighbourhoods characterized by filth and poverty (Mumford, 1979, pp. 496; 533–541), the single-family home located in a green suburban community was seen as an ideal living space. Suburbanization and urban sprawl were processes resulting from this ideal, and directly contrasted with the image of the dense city. It was no accident that these processes and their associated settlement patterns “became a national business” and were central to the post-war growth era (Phelps, 2015, p. 2).

However, the negative consequences associated with urban sprawl, such as soil consumption, high levels of motorized individual transport and greenhouse-gas emissions, led to a “battle against urban sprawl” (Charmes & Keil, 2015, p. 583). From the 1990s onwards, urban densification has become “a desirable development strategy” and “has been identified as a solution to environmental degradation deriving from urban sprawl” (Cavicchia & Cucca, 2020, p. 217). The advantages of urban densification, which include the reduction of housing costs, the increase of housing choice, the conversation of the countryside landscape, less need to travel by car and thus reduced fuel emissions and better access to services and facilities (Burton, 2000, p. 1969; Rosol, 2013, p. 2238) are “the substantiation of the contemporary celebration of urban densification, now seen as the standard remedy to sprawl” (Vaughan et al., 2009, p. 480).

Urban densification’s normative power derives from its capacity to integrate growth policies with principles of sustainable urban development (Krueger et al., 2019, p. 25). However, its basic idea is quite simple: the floor area or the number of dwellings on either unbuilt land or in existing buildings is increased. “Hard” densification that amounts to substantial change to neighbourhoods or vacant industrial sites through new or re-development is differentiated from “soft” changes such as subdivisions, or conversions of existing or vacant buildings (Bibby et al., 2020, pp. 103–104; Touati-Morel, 2015). Urban densification can thus be understood as the concrete material (and quantifiable) core of buzzword concepts such as New Urbanism, Smart Growth, Smart Cities, and Transit-oriented Development (Charmes & Keil, 2015, p. 583; Krueger et al., 2019, p. 25; Phelps, 2015, p. 37).

Due to its normative power, urban densification as a socio-material relation and a political-economic agenda is naturalized and “both obscures and limits urban politics” (Pérez, 2020, pp. 17–18). However, as countless publications demonstrate, urban densification is far from the objective and value-free win-win planning principle it is often portrayed as. “Density is not fixed, nor is it a singular process or ‘thing’. It is, rather, enrolled in all kinds of politics, contexts, and understandings” (Chen et al., 2020, p. 2). It is pertinent to outline three political dimensions that are influenced by urban densification’s normative power.

First, as Karampour outlines, urban planning has changed “to meet market needs and more flexible and negotiable approaches are designed to support market-friendly policies” (Karampour, 2021, p. 15). Urban densification plays a massive role within this shift, as, due to its quantitative character, it is often used as a bargaining tool to influence the public sector’s negotiating position towards private actors. Since urban densification provides the possibility to extract more value from buildable land (Robinson & Attuyer, 2020, p. 1) a potential increase in the attainable building density is a desirable target for developers. Tools such as density bonuses or minimum density thresholds (Touati-Morel, 2015, p. 603) enable the municipalities to couple demands for the provision of higher building densities that seem positive from a sustainability perspective, and which municipalities themselves are unable to fulfil because of their limited financial capacities. In the case of Tehran, a density bonus allows the municipality to generate income, while at the same time, it also increases the municipality’s dependence on private developers (Karampour, 2021, p. 15). Density bonuses have furthermore been provided to private developers, if they incorporate affordable housing units within their projects (Ryan & Enderle, 2012) or to increase energy-efficient renovations (Battisti & Campo, 2021) and housing construction rates in fast growing cities (Moos, 2017). In these cases, urban densification is not only an instrument to achieve more sustainable cities, but is used as a bargaining tool to ostensibly steer private developments in a specific direction.

Second, urban densification is a field of political contestation, especially at the neighbourhood level. In many cases, urban densification projects are framed as win-win projects, because of its advantages towards sustainability goals. Resistance against these win-win situations is often reviled as simply NIMBYism (Leffers & Ballamingie, 2013, pp. 146–147). However, scientific literature illuminates the complex socio-political and emotional phenomena behind resistance to urban densification. Even though proximity to densification projects, especially in low density neighbourhoods, increasingly leads to resistance from local residents (Brown & Glanz, 2018, p. 9; Wicki & Kaufmann, 2022, pp. 8–9), place-sensitive planning processes or the possibility of new amenities in a neighbourhood increase local support for urban densification projects (Wallin et al., 2018; Wicki & Kaufmann, 2022, p. 10). Especially in well-educated inner-city areas, resistance to urban densification is coupled to anti-growth sentiments and distrust of local political and economic elites. There either is a basic level of distrust that the promises of urban densification will be realised (Rosol, 2013, p. 2251), or “residents oppose the willingness to trade off significant policy commitments to social and environmental needs against heightened income generation from the built form” (Robinson & Attuyer, 2020, p. 6).

Third, urban densification “clearly has a class-based dimension” (Quastel et al., 2012, p. 1076), in that the municipal or regional socio-economic structure affects the type and volume of urban densification projects. Studies in France and Norway, for example, were able to demonstrate how the socio-economic status of a municipality not only influences the

preferred type of densification, but also reinforces existing patterns of socio-economic segregation. Soft densification policies are typically pursued in affluent municipalities with a high socio-economic status, while hard densification is more often found in municipalities with a lower socio-economic status that seek to attract new population groups (Cavicchia & Cucca, 2020; Rousseau, 2015; Touati-Morel, 2015). Also, urban densification is used as a catalyst for “growth machine” politics if municipalities aspire to increase their economic role in the city region (Touati-Morel, 2015). From this perspective, urban densification’s positive effects can either be accompanied or offset by negative consequences, such as segregation and displacement (Quastel et al., 2012; Stender & Walter, 2019).

While this rich body of literature illustrates the political and contested nature of urban densification, it remains pertinent to emphasise that this literature lacks empirical evidence that examines how urban densification was able to develop such a powerful role in spatial planning.

Methodological Framework

This article understands the emergence of urban densification as embedded in a long-term struggle between rival hegemonies. Therefore, the method of discourse analysis, which is relatively underutilised in planning studies, was selected in order to analyse the Alpine Rhine Valley case study. On the one hand, discourse analysis provides a methodical framework with which to analyse the long-term trajectories of socio-political demands (as Glasze (2007) illustrates on the example of francophony). On the other hand, Ernesto Laclau’s conception of hegemony explicitly pits the emergence of new hegemonies against the dissolution of established ones.

It is crucial to note that the author holds roles as local politician and planning practitioner in the region. These engagements permitted the author to explore implicit contextual knowledge and to access relevant possible documents, while also gaining access to interview partners. Although these engagements provide unique opportunities for this research, they also influence the interpretations necessary to conduct such an analysis and shape the findings presented in this article.

The Emergence of Hegemony

When we propose to understand urban densification as a hegemonial concept in spatial planning, we need to understand how hegemonies emerge and develop. Laclau and Mouffe see antagonisms as constitutive for all social formations (Glasze & Wullweber, 2014, p. 239); this basic assumption implies that discourses “are partly constituted in relation to other discourses with which they seek to align or challenge. The creation of a hegemonic discourse is the result of complex struggles in which opposed political forces (...) each seek to ‘universalize’ their

particular storylines and interests” (Griggs et al., 2017, p. 37). Hegemony is therefore not only the dominance of one social formation over another, but a discursive process through which articulations and projects that target that dominance achieve it (Nonhoff, 2007, p. 183).

Within the hegemonial process, articulations are the smallest pieces and can be understood as political demands (Nonhoff, 2007, pp. 182–183). Articulations and articulatory practices are produced by actors “who weld together a series of heterogeneous elements, though the resultant formations also structure actions, social behavior and institutions” (Griggs et al., 2017, p. 37). It is thus necessary to take into account the wider socio-political circumstances in which articulations for or against (for example) urban densification are placed (and by whom).

Articulations are thereby interwoven into wider hegemonial strategies, such as the logic of difference and the logic of equivalence. On the one hand, the logic of difference is a strategy that focuses on the destabilization of symbolic orders. It does so by picking and decoupling particular articulations from the web of meaning that is spun around a hegemony to make it contestable. On the other hand, “the logic of equivalence characterises how rival political projects connect together different demands by articulating their common opposition to something, which negates them” (Griggs & Howarth, 2019, p. 84). Articulations can therefore be used in different strategic contexts to either destabilize existing hegemonies or to form new hegemonic projects (Nonhoff, 2007, pp. 182–183).

This theoretical approach is operationalized for analysis through three steps. Dislocation is the first of these steps and “is the sine qua non for hegemonic articulation” (Torfing, 1999, p. 109). “Any discursive formation (...) is always vulnerable to dislocatory events” (Griggs & Howarth, 2019, p. 86) that “disrupt and destabilize symbolic orders” (Howarth, 2004, p. 261). Crises of existing hegemonies can be identified as points of departure for the analysis of the construction of new hegemonies. While this first step focuses on a logic of difference, the second step of the “suture” (see next sections) looks at the concurrency of difference and equivalence and how rival discourses struggle for hegemony. The third step pursues this argumentation by taking up the concepts of myth and social imaginary “to account for different modalities of hegemony construction” (Howarth, 2004, p. 263). While social imaginaries manage to “successfully conceal social dislocations by inscribing a wider range of social demands” (Howarth, 2004, p. 261), myths suture dislocations only incompletely. Therefore myths “tend to provide a surface on which unsatisfied demands are inscribed” and represent a vision of an ideal state of society which cannot be realized under the present circumstances (Torfing, 1999, p. 115).

Tracing Urban Densification's Pathway to Hegemony through Discourse Analysis

For the analysis of how and why urban densification emerged as a hegemonial discourse, a database consisting of a variety of documents published by the provincial government was compiled. These documents are either official publications published by the provincial spatial planning department or parliamentary materials such as protocols, government bills or parliamentary questions. Even though these documents all relate to provincial politics and policies, it is important to note that the documents cannot be treated homogenously, as would be necessary for lexicometrical analysis (Glasze, 2007). Rather, the speakers within the parliamentary protocols vary; government bills, parliamentary questions as well as documents published by the provincial planning department have been published with different purposes and different historical and political contexts. This database is enriched by ten expert interviews, two participatory observations in planning workshops, and media clippings to permit deeper analysis of emerging and competing hegemonies.

This “open corpus” of various data types was analysed according to the principles of constructivist grounded theory. The antagonism of urban sprawl and urban densification was used as a point “of departure to look at data, to listen to interviewees and to think analytically about the data” (Charmaz, 1996, p. 32). The composition of the corpus was guided by the context knowledge of the researcher and the research question. Constructivist grounded theory, with its iterative analytical process, is further supportive of discourse analysis with open corpuses (Glasze et al., 2021, p. 384) since new data sources can continuously be compared and mirrored with the existing material and the existing stage of analyses (Bading & Bosch, 2018; Charmaz, 1996). The corpus was then analysed through two phases: a deductive phase and an inductive phase.

Derived from the conceptual framework, the first phase of analysis was conducted deductively. On the one hand, Laclau's terminologies of dislocation, suture and myth were used to organize singular elements with regards to hegemony construction, while on the other hand, the antagonism of urban sprawl and urban densification was used to identify elements associated with these two termini. Elements can be viewed as the basic units of discourse and search grids for further analytic steps (Glasze et al., 2021, p. 381). Although the corpus has not reached its final state, the second phase of analysis began, while new material was constantly added and, at first, arranged deductively. Within this inductive phase, singular elements were connected to each other and coded accordingly, such that articulations formed. Articulations therefore represent a relation between two or more elements and necessitate interpretation by the researcher (Glasze et al., 2021, pp. 381–382). Articulations are reshaped, added or dropped during this iterative process until theoretical saturation is achieved. At this point, no new relationships between elements and articulations can be identified (Bading & Bosch,

2018, p. 81) and the research is once again mirrored with the conceptual framework (Charmaz, 1996, p. 47).

Case Study: The Alpine Rhine Valley

The Alpine Rhine Valley is the westernmost part of Austria and the economic and social centre of the Austrian province of Vorarlberg, with over two thirds of the province's population living in the region. The 29 municipalities that form the region are home to 270,984 inhabitants. However, the social and administrative structure of these municipalities is highly divergent; Dornbirn is the largest municipality, with just over 50,000 inhabitants. In contrast, Viktorsberg is the smallest municipality with a mere 415 inhabitants (Statistik Austria, 2022). Nonetheless, according to the Austrian constitution, all municipalities regardless of size are responsible for the execution of provincial spatial planning and building laws.

While the region was long characterized by poverty and emigration, industrialization beginning in the 1850s changed the region's perspectives: the exploitation of water power; infrastructural advancements, such as railway connections to Vienna and Zurich; and trade barriers imposed by the Austro-Hungarian Empire after 1873, set the region on a stable path towards growth (Feurstein, 2009, pp. 11–26). After WWII, the complete motorization of society and the division of Europe through the Iron Curtain strengthened the locational advantages of many Alpine valleys (Bätzing, 2015, pp. 204–205). Due to the dynamic economic development, the regional population grew by 130% between 1951 and 2021 (Statistik Austria, 2022; own calculations). The region even managed to successfully undergo transformations in the manufacturing industry. While textile industry had been the main economic branch until the 1970s, the Alpine Rhine Valley is now characterized by an industry highly specialized in electronics, metal processing as well as food and beverage production (Perlik et al., 2001, p. 249). Its gross regional product (GRP) per capita is one of the highest in Europe; between 2014 and 2018, the absolute GDP grew by 25.9 %, which represents the highest growth in Austria (Statistik Austria, 2022; own calculations).

Spatial planning (used in this article as a direct translation of the German word *Raumplanung*) has faced a double challenge in the region. On the one hand, many small municipalities had to cope with strong demographic and economic growth without corresponding expertise in their administrations. On the other hand, municipal autonomy in spatial planning is highly regarded throughout the province; as such, regional coordination has been relatively lax for many decades. The current spatial planning laws were not enacted until 1973, and a complete regional spatial development programme for the Alpine Rhine Valley, envisioned at the end of the 1960s, was in the end never decreed. After a regional plan to protect agricultural land was set up in 1977 (*Grünzone Rheintal*), it took until 2001 for a

new process to regionally coordinate spatial planning to commence (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 2006, pp. 46–47).

Figure 1: Location of the Alpine Rhine Valley

With the *vision rheintal* process, the provincial government and 29 municipalities in the Alpine Rhine Valley attempted to increase regional coordination, in order to better tackle challenges deriving from the uncoordinated settlement development (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 2006). Even though *vision rheintal* did not have any regulative competencies and ended in 2017, the process can be identified as one of the catalysts for massive changes to the provincial spatial planning system. A new funding scheme for spatial planning was set up; *Raumbild 2030*, a strategic planning concept, was passed by the provincial parliament; most importantly, the current spatial planning laws and the land transfer laws were reformed by the provincial parliament as well. Finally, *vision rheintal* was followed by *Kooperationsräume* programs (spaces of cooperation), aiming to concretize and implement the goals of *vision rheintal* on a smaller scale.

The Emergence of the Myth of Urban Densification in the Alpine Rhine Valley

While the previous section provided a short description of the regional socio-economic development and spatial planning system, this section discusses how and why urban

densification emerged as a planning principle in the Alpine Rhine Valley. To do so, it relies on three discourse analytical steps: dislocation, suture, and myth.

Dislocation: Waking up from the Rural Idyll

Since its political and administrative independence from the neighbouring province of Tyrol in 1861 and 1918 respectively, the province of Vorarlberg has been governed by the conservative Austrian People's Party (ÖVP). The conservative societal ideals, a liberal economic approach and high regard for land ownership are important discourses that have shaped the province's planning culture, and are deeply embedded in official policy of the people's party to this day (as further illustrated in the subsequent subsections). This made the self-financed single-family home the housing type of choice for official housing policies, as well as for large sections of the population. Lacking spatial planning regulations until the beginning of the 1970s, these mostly simple houses were primarily built on inherited land (Pichler, 2015, pp. 302–305). Even though hereditary division (*Realerbteilung*) led to a broad distribution of landownership in the population, making the single-family home boom possible in the first place, these small and dispersed building plots culminated in urban sprawl.

This liberal-pragmatic approach to spatial planning in the post-war period was the predominant strategy and was deemed to be “problem-oriented”, “tailor-made” and “practical” for the province's (spatial) development (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1996, p. 11). This approach also included a reluctance to resolve and decree a comprehensive provincial spatial development programme (*Landesentwicklungsprogramm*) and a comprehensive regional planning framework for the Alpine Rhine Valley (*Regionalplan Rheintal*) in the late 1960s. However, these uncompleted documents were the precursors for the first spatial planning law that came in effect in 1973, making Vorarlberg the last Austrian province to do so.

Within the annex of the first government bill, the inner conflict of the conservative people's party became visible. The pros and cons as to why it is reasonable for the government to restrict private property rights were carefully weighed against the need to somehow regulate post-war growth dynamics (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1972, p. 173). Subsequently, the provincial government decreed the *Grünzone Rheintal* (a protected green area in the Alpine Rhine Valley) in 1977 to protect the important agricultural lands in the Alpine Rhine Valley from urban sprawl. This region-wide plan to protect agricultural land is still being singled out as a positive example for soil protection and the success of the province's spatial planning policies (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1996, p. 11, 2017).

After these initial advances to regulate growth and to protect agricultural land, the logic of difference to connect urban sprawl to the negative consequence of land consumption became more dynamic during the 1980s. In 1983, an official publication of the provincial spatial planning department identified urban sprawl as the greatest problem of spatial

planning in the province. Lax regulation by the municipalities, responsible for planning and building within their municipal territory, was mentioned as one of the reasons for this development (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1983, p. 25). For all the harsh words regarding the negative consequences of urban sprawl in this publication from 1983, urban densification was not explicitly mentioned as a possible solution. Furthermore, in 1989 the provincial governor responsible for spatial planning replied to a parliamentary question about the problem of urban sprawl that the problem of land consumption could be solved by the provincial government's housing type of choice itself: The logic of his articulation was that through land-saving parcelling and reasonable allocation of building plots, even single-family homes can be seen as a moderate form of densification to protect soil (Vorarlberger Landtag, 1989, p. 3).

By the late 1980s and the early 1990s, the critics of the provincial governments' policies of spatial planning in general and of urban sprawl in particular became increasingly vocal, which led the provincial government to set up a soil protection concept (*Bodenschutzkonzept*) that was passed by the provincial parliament in 1992 (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1992). It included many strict measures to reduce land consumption and explicitly named urban densification as a central pillar for soil protection. However, with the soil protection concept being non-binding, strict measures have never, or only after many years, found their way into "hard" planning instruments; public funding for single-family homes continued. Until 1998 more than half of all new housing units built with public housing subsidies were single-family or row-houses (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 2021; own calculations).

The period between the 1960s and early 1990s was characterized by a contradictory movement. On the one hand, single-family home-induced urban sprawl was recognized as an important problem for the spatial development of the dynamic Alpine Rhine Valley. Through a logic of difference not only urban sprawl was criticized, but with it the entire set of planning policies of the provincial government. Especially from the mid-1970s onwards, the negative consequences for agricultural land were raised as the main articulations. Beginning in the 1980s, these concerns were embedded within a growing societal consciousness about ecology, illustrated by the election of the Green Party to the provincial parliament for the first time in 1984. Politicians from governing as well as opposition parties often linked the negative consequences of urban sprawl to the mountainous topography and rural tradition of the province, where only 25% of the territory can be used for settlement and intensive agriculture. On the other hand, however, the existing social imaginary of the single-family home remained stable and has been supported, not only in form of political statements, but also by concrete political projects, such as housing subsidies, overly generous zoning of buildable land by the municipalities and an inconsequent implementation of the soil protection concept. While the social imaginary of the single-family home has in some way been dislocated, until the 1990s

no connections between the growing environmental concerns and the socially traditional and economically liberal growth-oriented policies within which it is embedded had formed.

Suture: Urban Densification Becoming Popular

In the 1990s and early 2000s the logic of difference was still the primary discursive strategy, albeit with new articulations attached to the critique of urban sprawl. In one parliamentary question in 2002, the Green Party called for urban densification within core urban areas to keep soil sealing at a minimum and to reduce the need for further streets (Anfragebeantwortung Rauch, 2002). As it was many years previously, urban sprawl was connected to the negative environmental consequences of land consumption; however, now additional traffic was also connected to the articulations against urban sprawl. Crucially, urban densification was explicitly mentioned as a planning principle to tackle both: soil-sealing and extensive mobility. The amalgamation of planning challenges and the lack of consistent implementation of stricter planning regulations by the municipalities did not go unnoticed by the provincial government, and led to the implementation of the “vision rheintal” process beginning in 2001, to foster cooperation between the 29 municipalities in the Alpine Rhine Valley and to raise awareness of the importance of spatial planning (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 2006, p. 18). It could be described as a strategic planning process, which, crucially, did not have any formal jurisdictional planning competencies.

After *Grünzone Rheintal*, *vision rheintal* was the first initiative towards regional planning in the Alpine Rhine Valley since the failed regional plan of 1967. As hoped, this process was indeed able to raise awareness of the problems associated with urban sprawl, not only in the provincial government and parliament, but also in many municipalities. Mayors became aware of the necessity of regional coordination and spatial planning in general, and urban densification in particular for the development and competitiveness of the region. However, in the day-to-day politics of municipal spatial planning, this awareness has mostly been reduced to political lip-service (Interview Regional Development Manager, 20 October 2021). Still, the growing importance of urban densification in provincial planning policies can be identified by the number of documents of the provincial parliament that include the German term *Verdichtung* (densification), as illustrated in Table 1. While the term was nearly non-existent in political discussions up until the 1990s, it became a frequent component of parliamentary life from 1990 onwards. These periods can be identified as the time when the step of suture sets in.

pre 1985	1985-1989	1990-1994	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2019	2020-dato
2	1	3	4	4	4	10	16	1

Table 1: Mentions of the term “Verdichtung” (densification) in official documents of the Provincial Parliament

After the ecological turn in the 1980s and the rise of the logic of difference that criticized the planning and housing policies, which produced single-family-home-induced urban sprawl, another global process influenced the growing importance of urban densification from 2010 onwards. This is illustrated by the official documents as well as in all expert interviews. Besides the *vision rheintal* process that remained ongoing in the Alpine Rhine Valley until 2017, the 2008 financial crises and the effects of low interest rates as well as rising housing prices made urban densification a mainstay in the provincial parliament. Between 2010 and 2014, ten documents of the provincial parliament included the term, rising to 16 between 2015 and 2019. The pressure placed on urban densification to solve the housing crises increased in 2015, when a study commissioned by the provincial spatial planning department concluded that over 30,000 new housing units need to be constructed by 2031 (ÖIR GmbH, 2014, p. 55)

Beginning in 2010, it is possible to observe a shift in the discursive strategy in the public debate from a logic of difference to a logic of equivalence. In the past 12 years, urban densification has managed to unite different articulations from a constantly growing group of quite diverse actors. The “*Industriellenvereinigung*” (association of industrialists), *Verein Bodenfreiheit* (a NGO dedicated to soil protection) and the “*Arbeiterkammer*” (chamber of labour) all see urban densification as indispensable to the future development of the region, albeit with different articulations. The association of industrialists see urban density as central to the economic attractiveness of the Alpine Rhine Valley. Attached to that, professionals from the development and building sector connect urban densification to vague notions of urbanity such as the creative class, quality of life and multifunctionality. *Verein Bodenfreiheit*, however, argues from the perspective of soil protection and the chamber of labour calls for urban densification to improve housing provision and reduce housing prices.

This diverse constellation of actors supporting urban densification illustrates how dislocations open space “within which creative political subjects emerge” (Howarth, 2004, p. 261) to formulate their articulations through a logic of equivalence. *vision rheintal* played a crucial role in the emergence of these actors articulating themselves in favour of urban densification (Interview Regional Development Manager, 20 October 2021). To engage with this wide field of actors, the provincial government conducted a comprehensive two-year reform process between 2017 and 2019. By 2019, the entire planning system was overhauled, with new spatial planning and land transfer laws, new funding guidelines for regional planning, as well as the strategic planning concept *Raumbild 2030*. In all of these reformed or new planning instruments, urban densification plays a key role. The spatial planning department of the provincial government is conducting a series of studies and workshops in order to examine how urban densification can be implemented in the least contentious manner.

Myth: The Unfulfilled Promises of Urban Densification

The early 2000s saw a logic of equivalence prevail; it was supportive of urban densification and resulted in the emerging hegemony of urban densification becoming formally institutionalized into planning law. However, the case of the Alpine Rhine Valley is illustrative of the impossibility of urban densification achieving the status of a “social imaginary” for two reasons.

First, the durability of the built environment and property rights superimpose urban densification on a spatial context that was shaped by the social imaginary of the rural idyll of the single-family home, which for two decades in the economic boom after the second world war was an unchallenged hegemony. Between 1950 and 1980, the settlement area in the Alpine Rhine Valley tripled, while the population grew by 73% (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 1983, p. 25). The unregulated sprawl of urban development in the Alpine Rhine Valley (which was only partially restricted by the first spatial planning law in 1973 and *Grünzone Rheintal* in 1977) guaranteed social welfare, economic prosperity and development for large parts of the population. As was illustrated above, even though the dislocation of this discourse began in the 1970s, urban sprawl has intensified further, and for all the equivalent articulations and planning instruments supportive of urban densification, the single-family home as the epitome of urban sprawl remains a fixture of the Alpine Rhine Valley’s urbanization.

The second reason why urban densification will remain a myth is the number of articulations brought forward by powerful political actors. They reproduce the hegemony of single-family housing as a desirable societal objective and articulate negative effects linked to urban densification. While from the 1960s until the 1990s the logic of difference was used to articulate the negative consequences of urban sprawl, this same logic is now applied towards urban densification by using two particular articulations.

An example for the first articulation is brought forward in the agenda of the conservative people’s party of Vorarlberg for the provincial election in 2019. Even though they acknowledged that vertical densification should be permitted “where it seems appropriate” the prime mode of urban densification for large parts of the province, according to the people’s party, should be focussed on soft forms of densification, such as granny annexes and subdivisions of single-family houses or terraced housing (Vorarlberger Volkspartei, 2019, pp. 74–75). This articulation was also dominant at the two public planning workshops where participant observation was conducted. Denser urban structures were viewed very critically by a large number of attendees, because they “destroy the rural village character of the municipality”. However, as a compromise, soft forms of densification such as those mentioned in the election programme of the people’s party were agreed on by the attendees (public participatory event, 8 November 2021).

A second group of articulations that counter urban densification are predicated upon the dangers of anonymisation and immigration. Even though the chairman of the Austrian Association of Municipalities described urban densification as a “central issue” for all municipalities, at the same time, he referred to the dangers of anonymisation to indicate that single-family homes are still the housing type of choice for most municipalities (orf.at, 2021). Fears of anonymisation and non-integration of new inhabitants were also identified as key arguments against urban densification in a recent study of the provincial spatial planning department (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, 2018, p. 20). This is not necessarily an argument against international immigration, but rather criticises new inhabitants that “just live” in a municipality and fail to integrate into “village life”.

Even though urban densification manages to unite highly diverse actor constellations with a wide variety of articulations, it seems impossible for urban densification to reach the status of a social imaginary that completely sutures social dislocations. While urban sprawl is accepted as problematic, the single-family home on the edge of the city still represents a high social status, an ideal connected to the rural and conservative traditions of the region. The demand for single-family homes in the region is still high, and increased further during the COVID 19-pandemic (Vorarlberger Nachrichten, 2021). This results in a concurrency of equivalent articulations and actors supportive of urban densification, and a logic of difference that tries to link urban densification to negative effects.

Conclusion

The rejection of single-family-home-induced urban sprawl is unanimous across planning disciplines, and urban densification is widely embraced as a win-win principle in reducing the negative impacts of urban sprawl. Critical scholarship has gained deeper insight into the political nature of urban densification, by uncovering the hidden agendas and the class-relatedness that go hand-in-hand with growth and private-sector-driven spatial development. However, even though urban densification has become a prominently researched topic, there is a lack of research on how urban densification became so powerful as a normative concept in spatial planning.

This article illuminates urban densification’s emergence as a hegemonic discourse in spatial planning using the case study area of the Alpine Rhine Valley in the western Austrian province of Vorarlberg. By applying Ernesto Laclau’s conception of hegemony, the rivalling hegemonies of urban sprawl and urban densification as socio-materialities with conflicting discursive foundations were analysed. One key contribution of this article is therefore the identification of two main crises within this process: from the 1970s onwards, articulations linked to a logic of difference managed to slowly dislocate a liberal-conservative planning approach that idealized the single-family home. This dislocatory crisis was primarily initiated

by articulations that criticised the loss of agricultural land, and other negative environmental consequences.

The second dislocatory event is the housing crisis that became apparent after 2008. While in the 1970s environmental articulations relied on a logic of difference, since the 2000s, a variety of actors with diverse articulations confronted provincial planning policies. This resulted in a shift from a logic of difference, to a logic of equivalence that articulated urban densification as a solution for actor-specific problems of urban sprawl such as affordable housing, land consumption or economic competitiveness. However, the case study analysis reveals that urban densification cannot be understood as a hegemonic discourse in the sense of a social imaginary. Rather, the discursive struggle around urban densification is characterised by a concurrence of the logic of equivalence supportive of urban densification and a logic of difference that connects urban densification to negative consequences.

These critical articulations of urban densification have a shared discursive basis with articulations supportive of the single-family home. While the single-family home represents “rurality”, familiarity and traditional community values, urban densification stands for anonymity, lack of integration and the “non-rural”. The dichotomy of urban sprawl and urban densification is highly political and clearly points to class-based dimensions, underpinned by the region’s economically liberal and socially conservative values.

Urban densification in the case of the Alpine Rhine Valley is hence best encapsulated by Laclau’s conception of “myth”. Myths cannot fully suture societal dislocations and represent more of an ideal state envisioned by a variety of social actors. However, the question remains as to whether or not the hegemony of urban densification has been characterised by similar discursive processes and dislocatory events in other localities around the globe. Such research could revolve around discovering where actors supportive of urban densification position themselves in abstract political and societal processes, or how urban densification’s normative power is influenced by different socio-political contexts.

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